

INNOVATION THROUGH ICT IN THE TEACHING LEARNING OF WRITING SKILL IN ENGLISH AS SECOND LANGUAGE

Annotation:

The current situation regarding the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in ESL classrooms to teach writing skills is very promising, as it pertains to the whole process of teaching and learning. Every day, people rely on their writing skills to express themselves. This research aims to determine if and how technological tools improve students' writing skills in the classroom. Educators in today's schools must adapt to the ever-changing technological landscape by using newly developed tools and resources. Students are being given additional chances and tools to create more complex and grammatically accurate essays, tales, and letters via the use of technology in the classroom. Therefore the researcher made an attempt to study the relation of ICT with the language teaching in present days, to study the utility of ICT in teaching writing skill in English language and to study the trends of language classroom in relation to the ICT.

Keywords:

technology (ICT), writing skills.

Information about the authors

Dr. Bhabesh Pramanik
Principal, Dumkal College, Murshidabad, West Bengal, India

Introduction:

“Innovation opens up new vistas of knowledge and new dimensions to our imagination to make everyday life more meaningful and richer in depth and content.”

– Late Dr A. P. J. Abdul Kalam

Teachers, students, and researchers are all taking an interest in technology-based language education since it is a cutting-edge topic. Learners' performance in relation to effective writing skills was the focus of this research, which aimed to determine the impact of ICT and multimedia aided teaching on this outcome. This chapter addresses the challenges that prompted the proposed research, the study's aims and importance, and the need of information and communication technology (ICT) and multimedia technologies in education generally and English language education specifically. Although most educators still adhere to more conventional methods of instruction, there has been a recent uptick in the need for certified educators who can guide students through the integration of technology into English language classrooms. In today's world, where science and technology are advancing at a rapid pace, English language classes have the opportunity to transform and explore new models of teaching English through the use of multimedia technology. This technology, which incorporates audio, visual, and animation effects, is used to its fullest potential in these classes. —Thanks to the English-speaking world's fast-paced technological development, all nations except the most impoverished ones have easy access to American and British television and radio shows, films, records, and books (Broughton et al., 3). The use of multimedia technology in the classroom has been shown to significantly improve student learning and teacher engagement. The development of new technologies has paralleled the

expansion of the English language and is influencing the way we express ourselves. The expansion of multimedia has undoubtedly had a significant role in the expansion of the English language. As a result, there has been an explosion of writing on how to use technology into ESL classrooms. There has been a trend towards highlighting the inevitability of technology's involvement in education to the point that it threatens to replace instructors' human qualities. "Printed core materials, it was felt, would survive, but the demand for 'a better fit' meant that the variety of add-ons would grow, and as technology developed and became more available these supplements would be increasingly available online" (David Block, 165)

Statement of the Problem:

Students at all levels have been experiencing problems with inadequate and bad instruction in the areas of both reading and writing the English language. Internet, YouTube, Instant Relay Messenger, Smartphone, Projector, Television, E-books, Graphics, Mp3 Player, Video Player, Animations, and a plethora of other multimedia and information communication technologies are all around us these days. The field of English language instruction has benefited greatly from these technological advancements. The English language may be taught and learned with the use of many different kinds of information and communication technology, including multimedia. To make the most of new modern tools, however, many educators and students could lack the mindsets, perspectives, and technical know-how. Consequently, the purpose of this research is to examine how both instructors and students see the potential of information and communication technologies (ICT) and multimedia to enhance the instruction and acquisition of writing abilities in the English language. In light of the significance of information and communication technology (ICT) and multimedia technologies in education and other fields, the present investigation focuses on "**Innovation through ICT in the Teaching Learning of Writing Skill in English as Second Language**".

Significance of the Study:

Given the abundance of resources devoted to English language education, this study's theoretical contributions and practical insights into the effective use of multimedia technologies as teaching aids are of the utmost importance. Improving the successful use of ICT and multimedia technologies may be achieved by drawing on the discussion in this research to create better language instructional models, settings, and implementation tactics. The ability to effectively incorporate information and communication technology (ICT) and multimedia into the classroom is becoming more and more critical for educators, as is a positive attitude towards the use of these tools to achieve a range of pedagogical goals. Teachers must also possess sufficient self-assurance to effectively incorporate current technology into their lessons. An important first step in designing effective technology training programmes for both future and current educators is to gauge teachers' attitudes and levels of confidence about the use of information and communication technology (ICT) and multimedia. Improved utilisation of contemporary pedagogical tools is possible with the right kind of training in the right kind of setting.

Objective: The main objectives of the study are as follows-

- ✓ To study the relation of ICT with the language teaching in present days.
- ✓ To study the utility of ICT in teaching writing skill in English language.
- ✓ To study the trends of language classroom in relation to the ICT.

Discussion:

ICT's connection with language teaching in the present days: These days, cutting-edge electronics is integral to the instruction of almost every academic and professional field, from engineering and medical to law and management, the arts and language studies, and even entertainment. The

technology used in the classroom is not necessarily related to English in a disciplinary sense, but its textual character is closely intertwined with English studies, as pointed out by Hanrahan (2006) (Hanrahan, 32). Not only are today's scientific and language students proficient with computers, but they are also shaping the educational landscape of tomorrow. The majority of the world's universities and colleges provide some kind of information and communication technology (ICT) service or course related to education in an effort to meet the demands of more rigorous curricula for the study and instruction of contemporary languages, particularly English.

ICT based teaching and learning features:

Students' constant, anywhere-and-anytime access to course materials is a defining feature of instruction and learning supported by information and communication technologies. Certain methods of instruction and study are both synchronous (by means of online chat and video conferencing) and asynchronous (through means of online video classes, practical exercises, discussion forums, blogs, newsletters, etc.) (Cartelli, 2008). Anyone with access to the Internet may take part in an English language training course that is conducted entirely online. So that they aren't left out of the training opportunities that are accessible to the few, many students from remote areas may take part in a course. The ability to tailor instruction to each student's unique set of skills, experience, and goals is yet another major perk of technology-enhanced learning. With the use of particular software, instructors have the opportunity to supervise the results of the students' work, the level achieved by each and the possibility to update their online documents such as notes, images, videos. The most prevalent instruments that assure learners' interactivity and as a result the motivation to learn are:

(a) The student can exchange useful information on particular topics with the help of online facilities like forums. Usually, the forum moderator makes certain that the exchange of various viewpoints and beliefs do not go outside the set objectives and topics. Online chat rooms and various mailing lists stand for important socialization moments. Usually, the chat room and mailing list administrator should provide detailed information such as their next meetings and they should act like a filter for the informal requests of feedback during the communication process. These chat rooms and mailing lists connect the virtual community members with common interests and individuals charged with working on projects in a group setting.

(b) ICT based language learning develops both synchronously and asynchronously. In the former case, learners may ask questions to the teacher during a videoconference in real time and through the Internet live classrooms either by text or by audio when the internet computer connection is equipped with a microphone and speaker. In the later context, communication is asynchronous when learners communicate with teachers via emails, through discussion forums or when reading various course materials which are available online according to their own needs and schedules. So, the key concept is "interactivity between students and teacher", which is perceived as the opportunity for students to motivate the teaching process and to be motivated by it.

(c) The mixture of multiple approaches to learning is very prevalent at present. This mixed model of learning approach is called 'blended learning' which combines technology-based learning with other traditional resources in order to combine the flexibility of the new tools and the functionality of the traditional ones, such as the classroom setting and paper material for retaining the best features of each.

Contribution of ICT in ESL classroom The use of the computer in the classroom offers the opportunity for teachers and learners to interact in a meaningful and interesting way. As Rao P. S. (2019) says, "The teachers should understand the level of the students and try to adopt relevant teaching strategies of improving their writing skills that are more suitable for them. Moreover, the tasks that they choose for this purpose should be well-known to the ELLs and they should create interest among the learners" The use of integrating technology, such as the internet, enhances and

improves students overall writing abilities. According to Malloy and Gambrell (2006), “the internet exemplifies a growing literacy that engages readers of all ages and abilities.” Practicing writing can be done on websites, blogs, wikis, online forums, discussion boards, and social networking sites. There are several tools available online to help the students writing skills such as online dictionaries, vocabularies, grammar and, spelling checkers, encyclopedias, and online writing labs. Rojas (2011) declares that students improved the writing skill, because “they consider it could be learned by taking advantage of technological resources such as computers, blogs and, web pages” (p. 13). According to UNESCO (as cited in García & Marin, 2013): The term ICT is plural referring to a great many technologies and it is an all-encompassing term that includes the full gamut of electronic tools through which we gather, record and store information, and we exchange and distribute information to others (p. 428). Under the approach of ICT, the introduction of tools in the educational system aims to bring new experiences that promote language learning and interaction in the 21st century. Computer technology brings a set of advantages to promote and enhance language skills and it permits learners to develop their language competencies by interacting with the authentic material in an interesting and meaningful way. ICT gives the path to the online educational platform that offers the possibility to design language lessons in an interesting manner where the implementer can use diverse tools such as challenge board, cloze, columns, hangman, pop-ups, matching, word search, columns, rags to riches, jumbled words, picture-perfect, ordered list, and patterns to develop the learning. Computer-assisted language teaching and learning (CALL) enhances teachers’ practices and students’ independence, participation, and motivation towards language learning, that is, it plays an important role in the learning process to develop writing skills in an ESL classroom.

Future Trends in ICT based language classrooms:

An important challenge in language education is that of adapting various “student-centred approaches” to ICT based classrooms, and the following future trends can be highlighted:

- (a) ICT provides all time learning opportunities: ICT supports ‘anytime and anywhere’ learning frontier created by ICT based online learning communities. Educational institutions can help all kinds of learners to become lifelong learners, recognizing that educational / learning opportunities are available throughout their lives. Online ICT based learning provides answers to the problems of availability such as accessibility and cost; and the demand for flexibility in the aspects like time, place, and pace of language learning; technology-mediated learning and online learning will become major vehicles for fulfilling the needs of lifelong.
- (b) ICT supports constructive language learning: The theory of constructivism “views the central problem in explaining cognitive development as one of understanding how the mind succeeds in constructing relationships among objects and events”
- (c) Paperless virtual learning environment: In the future, most of the educational courses will increasingly become paperless and all course materials, including with syllabus and assignments will be included on a course web page, so that students can visit the website that will become an “open door” to the classroom. At present, teachers try to create a sense of community in the classroom; in the near future, the website will create a sense of community among all the members, and it will become a great way to inform and engage students across the curriculum.

Conclusion: The effect of ICT is developing positive attitudes and improving students' proficiency in writing English. This paper reviewed the contribution of Information and Communication Technology to develop writing skills in ESL classrooms. The use of technology occupies a major role in language learning. Technology provides interaction between teachers and learners, provides comprehensible input and output, helps learners to develop thinking skills, makes learning and teaching become more student-centered, promotes learners’ autonomy and, helps them feel more confident, and increases learners’ motivation to effectively learn a foreign language. Both students and instructors in today's

classrooms may profit from the utilization of technology, which is facilitated by the online learning platform.

References:

1. Choi & Ho. (2002). Exploring new literacies in online peer-learning environments. *Reading Online*, 6(1). Retrieved September 10, 2012.
2. Chua, Y.; Suliman, A. (2019). ICT: an effective platform to promote writing skills among Chinese primary school pupils. *Arab World English Journal*, 10(4), 223-237, doi:10.24093/awej/vol10no4.
3. Fernández-Batanero, J. M.; Montenegro Rueda, M.; Fernández Cerezo, J.; Román Gravan, P. (2021). Impact of ICT on writing and reading skills: a systematic review (2010-2020). *Texto Livre: Linguagem e Tecnologia*, 14(2), 1-12, doi:10.35699/1983-3652.2021.34055.
4. Emmer, E. T., & Stough, L. M. (2001). Classroom management: A critical part of educational psychology with implications for teacher education. *Educational Psychologist*, 36(2), 103-112.
5. Kelly, A., & Safford, K. (2009). Does teaching complex sentences have to be complicated? Lessons from children's online writing. *Literacy*, 43(3), 118-122.
6. Lawrence, S., McNeal, K., & Yildiz, M. (2007). Summer program helps adolescents merge technology, popular culture, reading, and writing for academic purposes. *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy*, 52(6), 483-494.
7. Lee, C. K. (2007). Affordances and text-making practices in online instant messaging.
8. Lenhart, A., Arafeh, S., Smith, A., & Macgill, A. R. (2008). *Writing, Technology and Teens*. Washington, DC: The Pew Internet & American Life Project.
9. Mullamaa, K. (2010). ICT in language learning – benefits and methodological implications. *International Education Studies*, 3(1), 38-44.
10. Silva, T.; Colleen, B. (2004). Research in teaching writing. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 24, 70-106, doi:10.1017/S0267190504000042.
11. Susilawati, P. P.; Sundayana, W. (2016). The use of Edmodo in teaching writing in a blended learning setting. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 5(2), 242-252, doi:10.17509/ijal.v5i2.1348
12. Yunus, M. M. (2007). Malaysian ESL teachers' use of ICT in their classrooms: Expectations and realities. *European Association for Computer Assisted Language Learning. ReCALL*, 19(1), 79-95.